

STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC FEATURES OF HOTEL BUSINESS TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Gaziyeva Nodira Rustam kizi,

1st year student of Linguistics faculty, Master's Department,

Uzbek State World Languages University

Supervisor: PhD, Associate Professor **Hakimov**

Hamidullo Inamovich

***Abstract:** This article discusses the studies of hotel business terminologies in English and Uzbek languages and it provides the research including hotel management, which can yield information about hotel business remains and the use of hotel terms and their originating, imprints of hotel business on any direction or hospitality used methods*

***Key words:** hotel business terms, comparison, terminology, management, lexical units, semasiology, setup, fees*

The hotel business terminology of the modern era testifies to trade routes, trends and traditions. We use hotel business terms with multiple meanings. One of the founding principles of terminology is that the study of concepts and concept structures or concept systems is essential. Any work concerning terminology is based on concepts and their delimitation. Concepts are not independent phenomena. They are always related to other concepts in one way or another, and form concept systems which can vary from fairly simple to extremely complex.

The term **Hollow Circle Setup** (*ichi bo'sh doirani o'rnatish*) is used to describe the Circular room arrangement in which tables/chairs all face one another. In this case, the definition does not mention the term addressing, but the term **Hollow Square Setup** (*ichi bo'sh kvadrat o'rnatish*) is used during an operation inside the Rectangular room arrangement in which tables/chairs all face one another that physically addresses within the facility and registering them in the system by matching the identification number with the identification number of the location

they are placed at. The examples below to illustrate the comparative study of hotel business terminologies in English and Uzbek languages with their definitions:

Hot Buttons - an issue that evokes emotional reactions, issues, and legal principles in hotel contracts that causes friction between planners and suppliers.

House Manager - the manager underneath the General Manager in ranking that is responsible for an individual hotel, unlike the General Manager—who covers more than one.

Intelligent Hotels - hotels that use state of the art technology to run operations.

Incentive Fee - a highly negotiated management fee provided to the manager based on incremental profitability and manager's operational expertise.

In the field of hotel management, texts are particularly useful in explaining the characteristics which cannot be easily conveyed by means of an image – for example the hotel business items of the hotel or other aspects requiring a verbal explanation. The examples below deal with the micro-structure of the hotel business long terminologies. The macro-structures are not dealt with here.

- **Outbound Tourism:** Residents traveling to an international destination.
- **Outside Vendor:** Any supplier that is not in-house nor a preferred vendor of the hotel.
- **Overbooking:** When more rooms are sold than are physically available to sell.

It should be emphasized that terminology research is one of the most difficult aspects of studying scientific and technical literature, as well as official working texts. The foundation of the hotel terminology system is a set of new phrases that reflect the unique characteristics of hotel business in contrast to other fields of study. Any professional translator's purpose is to achieve equivalence between the original and translated texts, as this is the foundation for their communicative equivalence.

The formation of the tourism terminosystem was different in Uzbek and English. Hotel business terminology in English is almost firmly established, while in Uzbek it is an evolving system.

The maximum closeness of both languages in the system of tourism terminology is observed on the basis of morphemes involved in the formation of the term. A productive way to form a term is to create suffixes and compound words for both languages. The key word in the terminological compound belongs to the category of nouns in both language models. However, in Uzbek the lexical unit uniting around the root word belongs to the category of adjectives, while in English it belongs to the category of nouns. For example,

Association Planner	Basic Fee
(noun+ noun)	(adj + noun)
Attrition Fees	Cold call
(noun + noun)	(adj + noun)
Butler Service	Competitive Set
(noun+ noun)	(adj + noun)

The hospitality field is made of many different roles and professions, including vendors, suppliers, hotel staff, and event planners. These teams work together to generate business ending in a boost of revenue and sales –and to put on stunning events. However, each sector has its own “lingo” that isn’t familiar to all those in the hospitality industry. In order to successfully conduct business with others outside of your realm of the industry, a mutual understanding of vocabulary is essential — whether you’re an expert event planner or a hotel sales manager, and every role in between.

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